

IDEAS-QA4EO

WP-2175 UAV for BRDF characterization

Validation report and
scientific roadmap

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This document is the Final Report of IDEAS-QA4EO, WP-2175 (UAV for BRDF characterization), covering activities completed on July 2021.

1.2 Acronyms and abbreviations

Table below summarizes the list of acronyms and abbreviations.

Acronym	Definition
QA4EO	Quality Assurance for Earth Observation
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
BRDF	Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function
S2	Copernicus Sentinel-2
ILS	Irradiance Light Sensor
GPS	Global Positioning System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
AGL	Above Ground Level
GSD	Ground Sample Distance
FOV	Field Of View
VZA	View Zenith Angle
VAA	View Azimuth Angle
SZA	Solar Zenith Angle
SAA	Solar Azimuth Angle
DN	Digital Number
VIS	Visible
RE	Red Edge
NIR	Near Infrared
PP	Principal Plane

2 ACHIEVEMENTS

WP2175 has demonstrated the potential of using UAV platform for surface reflectance and BRDF validation, an integrated approach that combine:

- Advanced UAV able to accomplish automatic and repeatable surveys collecting multiangular acquisitions;
- UAV multispectral camera designed to be compliant with radiometric characteristic of multispectral instrument installed on Sentinel-2 satellite constellation;
- the centimetres spatial resolution and the independence from atmospheric effects or cloud cover;
- the collection of dataset on different surfaces;
- the evaluation of model for BRDF estimation.

At present, there is a lack of extensive in-situ validation data to assess the quality of BRDF correction, then the goal was to demonstrate that the combination of a multispectral camera Sentinel-2 likes and the UAV flight potentials (as the capability of setting different view azimuth angles and view zenith angles), can improve the capability of BRDF modelling and validation.

In order to pursuit the project goals, we identified the following implementation steps:

- Integration of multispectral camera on UAV platform;

- system calibration
- flight planning
- dataset processing
- BRDF modelling

The project activities have involved state of art technologies for UAV multirotor as far as Multispectral Camera. Specific software and procedure have been developed to process dataset acquired during the surveys.

3 SYSTEM DESCRIPTION: MULTISPECTRAL CAMERA AND UAV MULTIROTOR

The evaluation and validation of BRDF using advanced UAV-based techniques requires the set-up of an appropriate payload, and the use of UAV capable to provide enough data acquired at different view azimuth and view zenith angles. Moreover, the repeatability of the survey represents an added value that can be obtained through a fixed mission plan which can be automatically execute by the UAV exploiting on-board sensors for positioning and trim maintenance. This section reports the characteristics of the UAV multirotor, the multispectral camera and the integration of the two.

3.1 UAV Multirotor

The UAV hexa-rotor used in this project, in Figure 1, is a Remotely Piloted Aircraft System (RPAS) with maximum take-off weight up to 8.1 kg, designed in order to allow high versatility. Its Plug & Play System allows the user to switch with ease between its various payloads, allowing a variety of applications to be satisfied with just a single platform. Real-time mission management is possible as well autonomous waypoint navigation. The UAV system has integrated Global Positioning System (GPS) and Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensors and auto-stabilization of flight in manual mode. The system is characterized by a maximum flight time up to 20 minutes. The Italian Civil Aviation Authority (ENAC) has given the Certification of Design attesting the compliance to Italian and European (EASA) laws. In order to ensure the safety of its users, this UAV is equipped with a Flight Termination System (FTS), that shuts down the entire system during emergency situations.

Figure 1: UAV Multirotor FlyNovex

It can use either a two axis or a three axis gimbal and can mount a variety of sensors including cameras, camcorders, thermal cameras and hyper-spectral, multi-spectral or Lidar sensors. Once in the air, Novex strictly follows a flight plan (unless interrupted by the pilot), allowing it to acquire information at a specific

frame rate and speed and therefore enabling it to perform high quality aero-photogrammetric and precision agriculture surveys.

Equipped with a return to base function, a parachute and a flight termination feature in, Novex is extremely safe, especially as it is able to continue flying with up to two engines out of use (not on the same arm). It can be flown in automatic, GPS or manual mode with the pilot able to intervene at any time if necessary.

Remote controlled gimbal for orienting MAIA camera between 0° and 90° respect to surface normal direction is possible as well as controls of orientation on the horizontal plane. These two latter properties are very useful for a complete BRDF characterization.

3.2 MAIA multispectral camera

The main instrument on board the UAV system is the MAIA S2 multispectral camera (Figure 2a), that permits the simultaneous acquisition of high-resolution images at various wavelength intervals in VIS/NIR (Visible/Near-Infrared) electromagnetic spectrum regions. In particular, the multispectral camera is equipped with the same wavelength intervals of the Sentinel-2 (S2) satellite, an Earth Observation (EO) mission developed by European Space Agency (ESA) and one of the missions belonging to the Copernicus Programme. In particular, S2 has been designed to perform terrestrial observations in support to services such as forest monitoring, land cover changes detection, and natural disaster management.

The imaging sensors features 1.2 Mpixel resolution, high sensitivity and global shutter technology, allowing the simultaneous acquisition of images free from motion artefacts. In Table 1, the viewing characteristics of the camera are provided in terms of AGL (Above Ground Level), GSD (Ground Sample Distance), FOV (Field OF View) and UAV speed. In addition, Table 2 reports the spectral bands that can be compared to those of the S2 satellite and Figure 3 shows the sensitivity of the bands. The system is also equipped with an Irradiance Light Sensor (ILS), see Figure 2b, measuring the level of the down-welling light in each band and allowing the correction for light changes during the survey, such as those caused by clouds. The use of the ILS is crucial for radiometric correction when passing from digital number (DN) to reflectance. It measures the radiation from the light source (e.g. the sun), providing reference values of the incident radiation for all the bands. ILS provides irradiance data at the exact time of shooting for each image and in each spectral band, substantially improving the accuracy of reflectance values in multi-temporal surveys. In addition, the ILS features a GNSS receiver that provides the geo-referencing information embedded into each image.

The acquired images are stored to an internal solid disk and the files name are automatically generated, depending on the absolute progressive number in the series and the date and time of the acquisition, according to the following code:

```
“yyyymmddhhmmssfff_xx-pppp.raw “
```

where:

- ‘yyyymmdd’ gives the date as year/month/day;
- ‘hhmmssfff’ gives the time as hour/minute/second/millisecond, in UTC time;
- ‘xx’ is the progressive serial number of the acquisition, reset at 00 each time the camera is switched on;
- ‘pppp’ is the progressive serial number of the image

In addition to the image file, a text log file that contains some useful information (timestamp, GNSS, exposure time, etc) are also saved.

Figure 2. MAIA S2 camera (a), and Irradiance Light Sensor module (ILS)(b).

AGL (m)	GSD (mm/pixel)	FOV (m ²)	Maximum UAV speed for 10 ms exposure (m/s) – (km/h)	Maximum UAV speed for 1 ms exposure (m/s) – (km/h)
50	23	30 × 23	2.3 – 8.4	23 – 84
75	35	45 × 34	3.5 – 12.7	35 – 127
100	47	60 × 45	4.7 – 16.9	47 – 169
150	70	90 × 68	7.0 – 25.3	70 – 253
200	94	120 × 90	9.4 – 33.8	94 – 338
300	141	180 × 135	14.1 – 50.6	141 – 506
400	188	240 × 180	18.8 – 67.5	188 – 675

Table 1. Field of view, ground resolution and flight speed for the MAIA multispectral camera at various altitudes above ground level.

Sensor	Band Interval (nm)	Color
S1	433-453	Violet
S2	457.5-522.5	Blue
S3	542.5-577.5	Green
S4	650-680	Red
S5	697.5-712.5	RedEdge 1
S6	732.5-747.5	Red Edge 2
S7	773-793	NIR 1
S8	784.5-899.53	NIR 2
S9	855-875	NIR 3

Table 2. Table of wavelength intervals of the filter-set settled in MAIA S2 multispectral camera.

Figure 3. Sensitivity of the optical bands of MAIA/S2 cameras.

3.3 Integrated system

The UAV system used in this study is shown in Figure 4 (with the camera on-board). It is a hexa-rotor with a maximum take-off weight up to 6 kg. It is equipped with a Plug & Play System which allows the pilot to switch between payloads. Real-time mission management is possible as well Autonomous Waypoint navigation. The UAV system has integrated Global Positioning System (GPS) and Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensors and auto-stabilization of flight in manual mode. The system is characterized by a maximum flight time up to 20 minutes. The Italian Civil Aviation Authority (ENAC) has given the Certification of Design attesting the compliance to Italian and European (EASA) laws. Remote controlled gimbal for orienting MAIA camera between 0° and 90° respect to surface normal direction is possible as well as controls of orientation on the horizontal plane. These two latter properties are very useful for a complete BRDF characterization.

Figure 4. UAV system mounting the MAIA S2 camera on flight.

4 SYSTEM CALIBRATION

This section presents the pre-operational tests carried out on the system before the on-flight operations. On one side, we verified the geometric and radiometric characteristics of MAIA multispectral camera. On the other side, we design the installation of the camera and its components on the UAV platform, programming and setting the flight unit for remote controlling of the acquisition geometry.

4.1 Camera Calibration

The geometric calibration plays, along with the radiometric calibration, a fundamental role to fully exploit the accuracy potential of multispectral system. In the MAIA camera, each mono-chromatic sensor is equipped with a fixed focus lens, whose focusing distance is set in laboratory and not adjustable by the user. A calibration certificate is provided for each sensor with a two-fold aim: (i) the calibrated interior orientation parameters can be used during photogrammetric processing; (ii) the calibration parameters are adopted to remove geometric distortion when co-registering the multi-band images and producing a combined multi-layer multi-channel image. For the geometrical characterization of the nine MAIA sensors, we report an ad-hoc test-field has been designed and arranged by the producer [6] in a dedicated facility at 3DOM-FBK laboratory (Figure 5a). A strict and repeatable acquisition protocol is followed, entailing some 40 camera positions (Figure 5b) at three different heights with roll diversity, guarantying an average intersection angle of about 75 degrees. The acquisition distance is 4 m, providing a ground sample distance (GSD) better than 2 mm. The obtained results show sub millimetric accuracy within the test-field volume for all bands, corresponding to a relative accuracy with respect to its diagonal (ca 3.8m) of about 1:11,000. Similar results have been observed with all the other units and will be presented in a future work. For the two example provided, the radial distortion graphs show that the used lenses are very well corrected with the maximum distortion below 15 pixels and each radial curve differing from the others for less than two pixels.

The radiometric correction is used in post-processing to correct for the component of irradiance light (normally the sun) and obtain the radiance of the elements (plants, terrain, etc.) that compose the scene. Radiometric calibration has been performed using the in-flight approach, which requires in-situ measurements using reflectance targets, solar photometers and radiative transfer codes. The producer offer three calibration methods: (i) automatic empirical correction; (ii) estimation of the correction using a radiometrically calibrated target; (iii) adoption of a rigorous correction method based on the use of an ad-hoc developed Irradiance Light Sensor (ILS). Since we equipped our UAV platform with ILS, the last of the three is the one we apply to our acquisitions.

Figure 5: Calibration test-field (a), and typical camera network (c) for the geometric calibration of the MAIA multispectral camera.

The use of a calibrated target may provide satisfactory results, although several issues may arise. In particular, if the target is imaged in varying lighting conditions (e.g., sunny or cloudy) that differ from other areas of the scene of interest, the calculated correction cannot be considered valid through the entire dataset.

The use of the ILS may improve the radiometric correction results. The ILS measures the radiation from the light source (e.g. the sun), providing reference values of the incident radiation for all the bands. This approach assumes that the radiation measured by the ILS is the same that irradiates the scene of interest. If this hypothesis is verified, the corrected reflectance value of the scene DN' for each Bi spectral band is computed according to:

$$DN'_i = \frac{1}{ILS_i} \cdot DN_i$$

being ILS_i the value of the light intensity detected by the ILS for each Bi spectral band.

The MAIA ILS is equipped with the same CMOS sensor of the MAIA camera. The measured ILS_i are synchronous with each image acquired by the MAIA camera.

4.2 Installation design

This phase is crucial to ensure the flight safety and the optimization of the UAV performances during the surveys, as the battery consumption, the motors heating and the trim maintenance.

The UAV is a delicate system in which the components have to be specifically selected and carefully located over the frame. Starting from the base UAV configuration we designed the supports for MAIA camera and the ILS module, including the supply and the wiring.

MAIA has been fastened on a 2-axis gimbal exploiting the inserts for screws already present in the middle part of its case (Figure 6). The gimbal fixing plane has passages for the wires for the connection with flight unit, allowing the automatic and remote control of the camera functionalities. Moreover, also the motor of the gimbal are connected with the flight unit, making possible the tilt control of the fixing plane and then the camera view zenith angle. On the other side of the fixing plane, we located the battery for power supply. The block including gimbal, camera and battery have been fixed on the center of the UAV frame in order to keep invariant the barycenter. The last aspect is critical for equal distribution of weight on the six motors of the UAV, avoiding overloads leading to failure or flight limitations.

Figure 6: Installation of MAIA Multispectral Camera on 2 axis gimbal of the hexarotor

Contrary to the multispectral camera, the ILS module needs to be placed on the upper side of the frame, allowing a full view of sky without shadow zones. We develop two specific metallic brackets, one for the ILS

and the other for its GPS antenna (Figure 7). In relation to their weights, they have been fastened on a proper horizontal distance respect to the center of the UAV frame. In order to The ILS synchronize information on the shots and receive power, the ILS needs a bus connection to MAIA multispectral camera. Finally, we program the Tx/Rx to control some of the camera functionalities and receive a live view during the survey, but also to allow the automatic control through mission planner software.

The UAV ready to flight including MAIA multispectral camera, ILS module with dedicated GPS antenna and battery for power supply, reaches a total weight of 4.5 kg and 16minutes of flight time.

Figure 7: ILS module with GPS antenna installed on top of the hexarotor

5 FLIGHT PLANNING

The flights have been planned using the Mission Planner software [<https://ardupilot.org/planner/index.html>].

The acquisition parameters of the MAIA multispectral camera can be set from the web interface. The file format can be set at 8, 10 or 12 bit; we choose to save the RAW image files at 12 bit, to catch more information. The acquisition mode is set to “continuous”, which means that the camera acquires images continuously, with a frame rate defined by the user. The “Live view” control is activated, thus it is possible to see the image as live streaming.

5.1 Vegetated Surface

The first set of measurements has been carried out on April 30, 2021, in a vegetated area, specifically a wheat field, close to the Borghesiana neighbourhood in Rome (see Figure 8 and Figure 9), during the passage of Sentinel-2.

Figure 8. Test site for vegetated area.

Figure 9. Top: The vegetated area in which the measurements have been collected. Lower left: Instrumentation. Lower right: The live view of the camera.

The measurement plan has been divided into two part, since the battery must be changed after about 20 minutes of flight. In the table below the acquisition details are shown.

Flight #	1		2
Date	30/04/2021		30/04/2021
Time (UTC+2)	Start: 12.30 Stop: 12.47 Duration ~ 16.30 min		Start: 12.57 Stop: 13.06 Duration ~ 09.13 min
Place	Lat. ~ 41.8761198 Lon. ~ 12.6682717		Lat. ~ 41.8761198 Lon. ~ 12.6682717
Altitude	120 m	Battery change	120 m
View Zenith Angle	0° - 40° Step: 10°		50° - 60° Step: 10°
View Azimuth Angle	0° - 330° Step: 30°		0° - 330° Step: 30°
Number of Observation	60		24
Sun Zenith Angle	27.3° at 12.45 UTC+2		27.3° at 12.45 UTC+2
Sun Azimuth Angle	168.6° at 12.45 UTC+2		168.6° at 12.45 UTC+2

Table 3. Acquisition details of the first measurement plan over vegetated area.

As it can be seen in Table 3, the observations have been collected for 6 different view zenith angles (VZA) and 12 different view azimuth angles (VAA), for a total of 84 measurement for each acquisition geometry. In particular, the UAV covers all the view azimuth angles for a fixed view zenith angle, for

example: for a view zenith angle of 30° the view azimuth angles covered are from 0° to 330° , then the inclination of the camera is increased to 10° and the azimuth angles from 0° to 330° are covered, and so on. See Figure 10 for the flight planning.

Figure 10. Scheme of the acquisition over the vegetated area.

The UAV remains in each waypoint for few seconds, during which the pilot enables the shot of the camera, and thus the sensor collects data.

5.2 Asphalt Surface

The second set of measurements has been carried out on July 3, 2021, in a paved area, specifically an asphalt surface, close to the Mathematical Physical and Natural Science Faculty of “Tor Vergata” University of Rome (see Figure 11 and Figure 12).

Figure 11. Test site for paved area.

Figure 12. The asphalt surface in which the measurements have been collected.

Also in this case the measurement plan has been divided into two part, due to the duration of the battery. In the table below the acquisition details are shown.

Flight #	1	Battery Change	2
Date	03/07/2021		03/07/2021
Time (UTC+2)	Start: 10.22 Stop: 10.33 Duration ~ 10.00 min		Start: 10.46 Stop: 10.54 Duration ~ 08.00 min
Place	Lat. ~ 41.8534721 Lon. ~ 12.6016214		Lat. ~ 41.8534721 Lon. ~ 12.6016214
Altitude	9 m		9 m
View Zenith Angle	0° - 30° Step: 10°		40° - 60° Step: 10°
View Azimuth Angle	0° - 330° Step: 30°		0° - 330° Step: 30°
Number of Observation	48		36
Sun Zenith Angle	37.1° at 10.40 UTC+2		37.1° at 10.40 UTC+2
Sun Azimuth Angle	108.5° at 10.40 UTC+2		108.5° at 10.40 UTC+2

Table 4. Acquisition details of the second measurement plan over paved area.

The measurements plan is the same of the first campaign collected over the vegetated area, then also in this case for each view zenith angle the UAV covers 12 view azimuth angles, for a total of 84 observation (see Table 4). Given the lower extension of the target surface compared to the previous vegetated area, the flight height has been set to 9 m: flying at high altitudes indeed, the sensor couldn't catch the target surface for large view zenith angles. The flight has been planned by using the Mission Planner software [<https://ardupilot.org/planner/index.html>]. See Figure 13 for the flight planning.

Figure 13. Scheme of the acquisition over the paved area.

6 DATASET PROCESSING

6.1 MAIA image-processing software

The software used to process the raw file of MAIA multispectral camera is provided by the producer. It is a professional software for geometric correction, coregistration and radiometric correction of the multispectral images in the RAW format (see Figure 14) obtained by the MAIA multispectral camera, with a tool for the creation of indices (e.g., NDVI) and the generation of false-colour images.

Figure 14. Example of RAW file collected by MAIA multispectral camera on vegetated area the 30 April 2021 at 10:41 UTC - VZA 30°, VAA 90°, band 7 (783 nm).

In order to prepare the dataset to be processed, the first step is to organize the whole acquired dataset, by dividing it on the basis of the acquisition geometry. The acquisition geometry of a specific shot can be derived by crossing the information contained in the file name and in the text log file (see 3.2), and, of course, by tracking the VZA and the VAA during the flight according to the flight scheduling.

For each waypoint, corresponding to a different acquisition geometry (all the combinations of VZA and VAA), a certain number of shots are collected with the selected frame rate. This allows to choose the best realization for each geometry of acquisition, then only one frame is selected. To do this, a preliminary analysis of the raw data is carried out with the MAIA image-processing software, paying attention to the coherence between files at the same VAA but at different VZA (see Figure 15), in order to avoid sharp shots and scenes not focused to the desired target.

Figure 15. Top: Graphical user interface of the MAIA image-processing software, the last button on the right allows to visualize the RAW data as a preview. Bottom: Example of the preliminary analysis to choose a proper image file within the whole data frame acquired at a specific acquisition geometry.

Once a single image file has been selected to represent the radiance measurement at a specific acquisition geometry, the whole dataset is organized in seven folders, each one containing the image files at a specific VZA, and subfolders, each one containing the image file at that VZA at a specific VAA, for a total of 84 image files.

The next step consists in applying the pre-processing chain to the RAW files, consisting in geometric correction, coregistration, radiometric correction, and finally the multi-TIFF image (see Figure 16). The geometric correction allows to generate the undistorted images through the calibration parameters included with each sensor. The coregistration between the different bands (stitching) is based on a reference image and allows the pixel-by-pixel convergence. The radial radiometric correction corrects the border effect of the image which can arise due to lens curvature. The radiometric correction is used in post-processing to correct for the component of irradiance light (normally the sun) and obtain the radiance of the elements (plants, terrain, etc) that compose the scene. Radiometric calibration is implemented by the MAIA proprietary software application, adopting a rigorous correction method based on the use of ILS. The method assumes that radiation measured by the ILS is the same that irradiates the scene of interest. The corrected reflectance value of the scene DN'_i for each B_i spectral band is computed according to:

$$DN'_i = \frac{1}{ILS_i} \cdot DN_i$$

being ILS_i the value of the light intensity detected by the ILS for each B_i spectral band, [6].

Figure 16. Graphical user interface of the MAIA image-processing software for the creation of a multi-TIFF image by applying the correction processes.

A text file containing the “borders” (pixel coordinates) which account for “no data” edges is generated after the stitching process and it is saved. The text file “borders” allows to crop all the images in equal measure by removing the “no data” border (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Graphical user interface of the MAIA image-processing software for the cropping of the images to avoid "no data" border.

The "Create View" menu (see Figure 18) uses the multi-TIFF images to generate multi-channel images. In this operation the acquisition file format passes from 12 bit (DN from 0 to 4096) to 16 bit (DN from 0 to 65536).

Figure 18. graphical user interface of the MAIA image processing software for the creation of multi-channel images.

7 BIDIRECTIONAL REFLECTANCE DISTRIBUTION FUNCTION (BRDF)

In this section, we report a brief theoretical background and the result of the elaborations in terms of polar plots of the measured reflectance and the estimation of model parameters of the BRDF function over two surfaces: vegetation and asphalt.

7.1 Theoretical background

Natural surfaces reflect light in different ways and different amounts according to the viewing and illumination conditions and the reflective character of the surface (Figure 19). Thus, such behaviour depends on the level of anisotropy of the surface itself, which depends on the optical properties of the surface elements and their geometric and volumetric mutual positioning. The level of surface anisotropy is quantitatively described by the BRDF.

Figure 19. Causes for land surface reflectance anisotropy (Wolfgang Lucht, 1997).

BRDF correction techniques are developed to normalize the observation to a standard angular configuration, or alternatively, as an intrinsic signature of the considered surface that can be used to retrieve relevant bio-geophysical variables. However, there is currently a lack of extensive in-situ validation data to assess the quality of this correction. One of the major challenges in this respect is the spatial representativeness of the reference data and its comparability to the satellite pixel scale.

Most of the researches dedicated to surface reflectance and BRDF validation, utilize ground-based multi-angular measuring instruments or satellite-based multi-angular data. Although reflectance at any observation angle can be obtained using a ground-based multi-angular measurement instrument, the complicated measurement process is time- and labor-consuming, and subject to large human interference, and more importantly, only "point" measurements can be conducted. Although satellite remote sensing has the characteristics of large area synchronous observation and can carry out multi-angular "surface" measurements, the satellites with multi-angular imaging capability can work only from a few observation angles (such as five viewing angles for CHRIS and nine viewing angles for MISR) [8]. Space platform has difficulty in obtaining data from multiple observation angles, which limits the research and application of multi-angular remote sensing based on satellites. Moreover, space system with multi-angular imaging capability has been limited by poor revisiting times and/or coarse spatial resolutions so that hardly meets the needs of precise characterization. The development of unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) technology provides the possibility of solving the above problems. However, vertical observation data [2; 11] are mostly used in current applications of UAV-based acquisition as for example vegetation physical and chemical parameters estimation, and UAV-based multi-angular remote sensing is rarely used. As multi

angular remote sensing has excellent performance in both ground and satellite applications, UAV-based multi-angular remote sensing should have greater potential and application prospects. Roosjen et al., used UAV multi-angular reflectance data to retrieve the chlorophyll content and LAI of potatoes. Moving to QA4EO, the objective of WP 2175 is intended to study whether UAV multi-angular acquisition can be used to improve the modelling of BRDF and then to improve cal/val activities for the satellite, in particular Sentinel 2, calculated reflectance of a specific surface.

7.2 BRDF Models

A BRDF model is a parametrization of the Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function, which is able to simulate the reflectance anisotropy, that is the land surface reflectance at any view and illumination geometry.

The approach is based on the inversion of the model with observed data (multi-angular measurements made by different type of devices such as field instruments or satellites) in order to find the model's parameters which best fit the measurements, by computing the root-mean squared error between the observed and modeled reflectance. After that it is possible to run the model in the forward direction to predict reflectance at any sun-view geometry conditions.

Different types of models have been developed during the years. In our work we will use the kernel-driven RossThick-LiSparse (Ross-Li) semiempirical linear model, which has been used for the processing of MODIS land surface measurements [3].

Linear models are characterized by a sum of different terms, each one representing a basic scattering type:

$$R(\theta_s, \theta_v, \varphi) = K_0 + K_1 F_1(\theta_s, \theta_v, \varphi) + K_2 F_2(\theta_s, \theta_v, \varphi) + \dots + K_n F_n(\theta_s, \theta_v, \varphi)$$

where R is the simulated reflectance, θ_s is the solar zenith angle, θ_v is the view zenith angle (VZA), φ is the relative azimuth angle between the directions of the incoming and outgoing light rays, n is the number of parameters, K_i are the free model's parameters which must be retrieved through the model's inversion, F_i are the kernels of the model. In the case of the Ross-Li model the number of the parameters is three ($n = 2$). Each coefficient K_i represents the proportion of isotropic reflection (K_0), geometric optical reflection (K_1) and volume scattering (K_2), [5]. The kernels describe the fundamental physical theory of the different type of scattering. F_2 considers the radiative transfer-type volumetric scattering and it is called the RossThick kernel for its assumption of a dense leaf canopy [3], [4]; its expression is derived by Roujean et al. [9].

$$F_2 = \frac{4}{3\pi} \frac{1}{\cos\theta_s + \cos\theta_v} \left[\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \xi \right) \cos\xi + \sin\xi \right] - \frac{1}{3}$$

where ξ is the phase angle:

$$\cos\xi = \cos\theta_s \cos\theta_v + \sin\theta_s \sin\theta_v \cos\varphi$$

F_1 represents the geometric-optical surface scattering, it is called the LiSparse kernel for its assumption of a sparse ensemble of surface objects casting shadow on the background, [3], [4].

$$F_1 = \frac{m}{\pi} (t - \sin t \cos t - \pi) + \frac{1 + \cos\xi}{2\cos\theta_s \cos\theta_v}$$

$$\cos t = \frac{2}{m} \sqrt{\Delta^2 + (\tan\theta_s \tan\theta_v \sin\varphi)^2}$$

$$m = \frac{1}{\cos\theta_s} + \frac{1}{\cos\theta_v}$$

where Δ quantifies the horizontal distance between the sun and view directions:

$$\Delta(\theta_s, \theta_v, \varphi) = \sqrt{\tan^2\theta_s + \tan^2\theta_v - 2\tan\theta_s\tan\theta_v\cos\varphi}$$

The term $\cos \varphi$ should be constrained in the range [-1,1]; values outside of this range imply no overlap area between the view and solar shadows and should be neglected, [1]. Full derivations of the RossThick and the LiSparse kernels can be found in Wanner et al. [12].

There have been carried out some studies which show that kernel-based models with their three parameters give reasonable fits to field-measured BRDF data sets, that is they are able to accurately represent the shapes of naturally occurring BRDF's and this is an essential condition of the BRDF model to be used, [1].

Since that the Ross-Li model is linear and it has few parameters, it can be more easily and quickly inverted. Besides it is preferable when the dataset for the inversion of the model is characterized by a sparse angular sampling, albeit models with more parameters, may be generally highly accurate than models with few parameters, [9].

The performance of a model is driven by the accuracy of the determined parameters; therefore, it is very important the quality of the data used for the inversion, from which the parameters have to be retrieved. The field data should be acquired under sufficient angular sampling ("directional resolution"), under clear-sky condition and in a brief time interval, so that the surface's characteristics and the atmospheric conditions don't change during the acquisition period. Moreover, the performance of a model to simulate the directional signature of surface reflectance, definitively depends also by the properties and accuracy of the model [10].

In the case of the Ross-Li model, the kernels don't consider the hot spot effect (which accounts for the reflectance increase that takes place when the sun and the view directions are coincident). In order to supply this gap, another model, called Ross-Li-Maignan, a version of the Ross-Li model accounting for the hot spot process, has been also developed [1].

7.3 Elaboration of the measured reflectance

In this section, the results of the elaboration of the measurements collected with the MAIA multispectral camera over vegetation (30 April 2021) and asphalt (3 July 2021) are presented.

Once MAIA data have been pre-processed by means of the MAIA image-processing software (see 6.1), a multi-channel TIFF image in the nine bands (see Table 2) of the MAIA multispectral sensor is available for each acquisition geometry. For more clarity, the list of all the configuration geometries for each image file is provided below (see Figure 20), for a total of 84 image files each one representing a specific acquisition geometry.

Figure 20. Scheme of the whole MAIA dataset: all the combinations between VZA and VAA for each band.

Before representing the collected data as BRDF values, other processing operations are needed.

First, the full image must be cut (Figure 21) in order to catch the area affected by the target surface, since that it is needed to observe a homogeneous surface to collect BRDF data. This operation is essential in the case of large value of VZA since the more the inclination of the camera is high the more the observed area shifts, and the target goes outside from the scene. Besides, this effect increases with the flying height, thus, in our case, for the dataset collected on the vegetated area (flight altitude: 120 m, see Table 3).

Figure 21. Example of crop on the full image collected with MAIA to avoid not homogeneous area.

MAIA multispectral camera collects radiance measurements, which have been already converted to reflectance values thanks to the ILS sensor on board UAV platform, which accounts for the sun irradiance

(see 6.1). The reflectance values range from 0 to 65535 (the file format of the multi-channel TIFF output of the MAIA image-processing software is 16 bit); then all the values have been scaled between 0 and 1.

As already mentioned, the dataset collected with the MAIA multispectral camera consists of an image for each acquisition geometry. In order to get a unique value of reflectance for each specific acquisition geometry the average of the reflectance value for the cropped images is carried out.

BRDF measurements are usually represented in a polar coordinate system to better interpret and compare the spectro-directional data. In Figure 22 the configuration of the whole set of the collected measurements is shown for the two missions performed for the different surfaces (vegetated area the 30 April 2021, paved area the 3 July 2021, see 5). The concentric rings represent the sensor view zenith angle (VZA) ranging from 0° to 60°, while the radial lines correspond to the sensor view azimuth angle (VAA) ranging from 0° to 330°. The polar plot is oriented towards the North.

A certain degree of uncertainty is related to the change in the illumination direction during the survey. As the survey time is about 10 minutes, It is assumed that the Sun lies in a fixed position during the flight (SZA and SAA have been selected at half of the survey). Actually, sun slightly changes its position resulting in a negligible variation of the illumination direction during the flight. Another source of uncertainty could arise from UAV positioning instrumental errors (corrupted GPS signal, compass noise) and environmental variability during the flight (wind gusts). Thus, some minor discrepancies in the results could be observed (such as outliers in the BRDF values represented in the polar plots).

#	VZA	VAA
1)	0°	0°, 30°, 60°, 90°, 120°, 150°, 180°, 210°, 240°, 270°, 300°, 330°
2)	10°	0°, 30°, 60°, 90°, 120°, 150°, 180°, 210°, 240°, 270°, 300°, 330°
3)	20°	0°, 30°, 60°, 90°, 120°, 150°, 180°, 210°, 240°, 270°, 300°, 330°
4)	30°	0°, 30°, 60°, 90°, 120°, 150°, 180°, 210°, 240°, 270°, 300°, 330°
5)	40°	0°, 30°, 60°, 90°, 120°, 150°, 180°, 210°, 240°, 270°, 300°, 330°
6)	50°	0°, 30°, 60°, 90°, 120°, 150°, 180°, 210°, 240°, 270°, 300°, 330°
7)	60°	0°, 30°, 60°, 90°, 120°, 150°, 180°, 210°, 240°, 270°, 300°, 330°

Figure 22. Design of the measurement scheme, for a total of 84 measurements positions; the green squares indicate the azimuth and zenith angles of the measurement points.

7.3.1 BRDF Measurements - Vegetated Surface

In this section, the BRDF polar plots for the measurements collected the 30 April 2021 on vegetated area are shown for the different bands of the MAIA multispectral camera (see Table 2).

Figure 23 shows the polar coordinate system representing the Sun position (yellow star), the measurements points (green squares), the Principal Plane (PP) and the Cross Plane (CP) for the acquisition geometry of the mission under consideration. The Principal Plane is identified by a relative azimuth angle between the Sun and the sensor ($\varphi_{rel} = \varphi_{sun} - \varphi_{view}$) of 0° and 180° ; the Cross Plane is orthogonal respect to the Principal Plane. The two planes identify the portion of the polar coordinate system characterized by a backward direction of the scattered light (on the right of the CP, on the same side respect to the Sun) and a forward direction of the scattered light (on the left of the CP, on the opposite side respect to the Sun). This means that for all the measurements points (green squares) lying on the right part of the CP we talk about backward scattering, while for all the measurements points lying to the left part of the CP we speak of forward scattering. This is a key concept since that the spectral behaviour of surfaces is explainable on the basis of the BRDF distribution between these two directions (backward and forward). For example, it is known that surfaces with a certain degree of roughness, such as vegetated area, generally exhibit a peak of reflectance in the backward direction, while flat surfaces, such as a calm sea surface, are usually characterized by high values of reflectance in the forward direction (i.e. specular scattering). For more clarity, in Figure 24 a polar coordinate system in 3D which represents the geometry configuration of the illumination and observing directions in the case of backward and forward scattering is shown. Figure 24 is obtained by means of AnisView [<https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/scientific-tool/anisview>], a software for the visualization of the BRDF, by setting the input parameters to $VZA=60^\circ$, $SZA=30^\circ$, $\varphi_{rel}=180^\circ$ (backward scattering direction), $\varphi_{rel}=0^\circ$ (forward scattering direction). As it can be seen in Figure 24, the backscattering direction corresponds to the configuration in which the sensor is facing away from the Sun, while when the sensor is facing the Sun the observation direction is forward, [5].

Figure 23. Polar coordinate system representing the PP (red dotted line), CP (blue dotted line), Sun position (yellow star), measurements points (green squares) and black arrows indicating the backward direction and the forward direction for the configuration geometry of the 30 April 2021 over vegetated area.

Figure 24. On the right: sensor on the same side as the Sun - backward direction; parameters set: $VZA=60^\circ$, $SZA=30^\circ$, $\phi_{rel}=180^\circ$. On the left: sensor on the opposite side respect to the Sun - forward direction; parameters set: $VZA=60^\circ$, $SZA=30^\circ$, $\phi_{rel}=0^\circ$.

Figure 25 shows the spectral signature for MAIA measurements carried out in the vegetated area at different VZA (from 0° to 60°) for a fixed VAA of 180°, which corresponds to the direction close to the PP (where the Sun lies) in the backward scattering direction. The spectral signature displays the radiation

reflected as a function of the wavelength; for the observed area is clearly referable to a target of green vegetation (Figure 25). In order to highlight the instrument sensibility, the spectral signature has been evaluated along the PP direction, which is characterized by the maximum BRDF variability respect to VZA. Given a fixed sun position, the increasing of VZA leads to an overall increasing of the reflectance value in each band Figure 25.

Figure 25. Spectral signature of the vegetated area observed by MAIA at different view zenith angles (from 0° to 60°) for a view azimuth angle of 180° (close the PP).

In Figure 26, the polar plots for each band for the BRDF measurements collected over vegetated area are shown.

Given the wide variability of the reflectance values in the different bands for vegetated surfaces two different colour scales for VIS (Visible) and RE-NIR (Red Edge-Near Infrared) bands have been used for a better visualization of the BRDF dynamic. The Sun position at the time of the flight is also reported (white star), which is characterized by a SZA of 27.3° and a SAA of 168.6° (see Table 3 for the mission details). This is an approximation since that during the duration of the flight (less than 30 minutes) the Sun zenith and azimuth angle varies, even if only slightly.

Figure 26. BRDF polar plots for S2-S9 bands of MAIA multispectral camera for the measurements collected the 30 April 2021 over vegetated area.

For VIS bands, the main variations of the BRDF are observed close to the principal plane, i.e. in the plane where the Sun lies. A clear hot spot effect can be seen for the VIS bands in correspondence of the position of the Sun. For VIS bands the BRDF shows indeed a distribution with high values in the backward direction, as expected from a vegetated area. In the red band, indeed, the shadows are more pronounced due to the chlorophyll absorption of radiance and thus we observe lowest BRDF in the forward scattering direction and highest BRDF in the backward scattering direction. This is because when the sensor is facing away from the Sun (backscattering direction) it sees the well-illuminated side of the vegetation, which gives higher reflectance; when the sensor is facing the Sun (forward scattering direction), it sees instead the shadowed side of the vegetation, which leads to lower reflectance [8]. In general, the dark side of the surface is characterized by lower reflectance, while the lit side of the surface gives highest reflectance. Besides, the more the shadow effects are pronounced the more the anisotropic effect is strong. This is the reason why in the RE and NIR bands we observe no anisotropic effect (except band 5 at 705 nm) and the reflectance is independent of the view azimuth direction, while it grows by increasing VZA, [8].

7.3.2 BRDF Measurements - Asphalt Surface

In this section, the BRDF polar plots for the measurements collected the 3 July 2021 on paved area are shown for the different bands of the MAIA multispectral camera (see Table 2).

Figure 27 shows the polar coordinate system representing the Sun position (yellow star), the measurements points (green squares), the Principal Plane (PP) and the Cross Plane (CP) for the acquisition geometry of the mission under consideration. PP and CP identify the portion of the polar coordinate system characterized by a backward direction of the scattered light (on the right of the CP, on the same side respect to the Sun) and a forward direction of the scattered light (on the left of the CP, on the opposite side respect to the Sun). As already mentioned (see 7.3.1), all the measurements points (green squares) lying on the right part of the CP are characterized by a backward direction of the scattered light, while all the measurements points lying to the left part of the CP are characterized by a forward direction of the scattered light. See also the polar coordinate system in 3D in Figure 24 to have clear the geometry configuration of the observing sensor and illumination direction for both backward and forward scattering.

Figure 27. Polar coordinate system representing the PP (red dotted line), CP (blue dotted line), Sun position (yellow star), measurements points (green squares) and black arrows indicating the backward direction and the forward direction for the configuration geometry of the 30 April 2021 over vegetated area.

Figure 28 shows the spectral signature for MAIA measurements carried out over the paved area at different VZA (from 0° to 60°) for a fixed VAA of 120°, which corresponds to the direction close to the PP (where the Sun lies) in the backward scattering direction. As before, the spectral signature has been evaluated along the PP direction, which is characterized by the maximum BRDF variability respect to VZA. The reflectance values show an overall increment with the increasing of VZA, even if there are some exceptions: the VZA equal to 40° is characterized by higher reflectance than the VZA equal to 50° and 60°. This can be explained by the Sun view angle (37.1°, see Table 4), which is much closer to 40° than to 50° and 60°. Indeed, the literature evidences that the maximum values of reflectance should be found in correspondence of the Sun position. In general, the trend of the spectral signature along the VZA strictly depends on the position of the Sun respect to the observation geometry, and the peak of reflectance should be found in correspondence of SZA and SAA.

Figure 28. Spectral signature of the asphalt area observed by MAIA at different view zenith angles (from 0° to 60°) for a view azimuth angle of 120° (close the PP).

In Figure 29 the polar plots for each band for the BRDF measurements collected over asphalt area are shown.

The Sun position at the time of the flight is also reported (white star), which is characterized by a SZA of 37.1° and a SAA of 108.5° (see Table 4 for the mission details). This is an approximation since that during the duration of the flight (less than 20 minutes) the Sun zenith and azimuth angle varies, even if only slightly.

Figure 29. BRDF polar plots for S1-S9 bands of MAIA multispectral camera for the measurements collected the 3 July 2021 over paved area.

As Figure 29 shows, the surface presents for each band an anisotropic behaviour with a peak of reflectance in the backward direction. The main variations of the BRDF are observed close to the principal plane, i.e. in the plane where the Sun lies. The hot spot effect can be observed in correspondence of the position of the Sun. The BRDF shows indeed a distribution with high values in the backward direction. In general, as already mentioned, the dark side of the surface (which is observed by the sensor when it is facing the Sun) is characterized by lower reflectance, while the lit side of the surface (which is observed by the sensor when it is facing away from the Sun) gives highest reflectance [8].

7.4 BRDF Modelling

In this section, the results of the implementation of BRDF models generated on the basis of the measurements collected with the MAIA multispectral camera over vegetation (30 April 2021) and asphalt (3 July 2021) are presented.

Once MAIA data have been elaborated and BRDF values have been extracted for each VZA and VAA, the dataset can be used to invert a BRDF model to find the parameters of the model which best fit the measurements. There are several BRDF models, we have been used the semi-empirical Ross-Li model, which describes the BRDF as a function of three parameters:

$$R(\theta_s, \theta_v, \varphi) = K_0 + K_1 F_1(\theta_s, \theta_v, \varphi) + K_2 F_2(\theta_s, \theta_v, \varphi)$$

For further details about the model see 7.2.

The kernels of the model (F_1 , F_2) can be computed (see the formulas in 7.2) by knowing the Sun and acquisition geometries at the time in which the measurements have been collected. Given the reflectance observations (R), that is the MAIA measurements, at different illumination and viewing angles (θ_s , θ_v , φ), it is possible to derive model parameters (K_0 , K_1 , K_2) by means of the least squared method. The MatLab Curve Fitting Toolbox [<https://it.mathworks.com/help/curvefit/index.html>] has been used to fit the measurements; the toolbox uses the method of least squares when fitting data. The least squares method allows indeed to estimate the model coefficients, by minimizing the summed squared of residuals, which are defined as the difference between the observed values and the fitted values.

When the model has been inverted and the parameters have been retrieved, they can be used in forward model runs to reproduce reflectance for any Sun-View geometry [7]. In this section we also make a

comparison between the BRDF measured and the BRDF modelled, obtained by running the forward model for the same acquisition geometry of the measured data.

7.4.1 BRDF Model – Vegetated Surface

In this section, we present the BRDF model generated from the MAIA multispectral camera data when observing the vegetated surface (mission of the 30 April 2021, see Table 3)

After the processing of the BRDF values for the collected measurements, the first step which must be done in order to invert the model, is to compute the kernels of the model (F_1 , F_2) for the specific acquisition geometry. This has been achieved by means of a Python code already existing.

Knowing reflectance (R , MAIA measurements) and kernels (F_1 , F_2) for different Sun-viewing angles (θ_s , θ_v , φ), the parameters of the model (K_0 , K_1 , K_2) are estimated and listed in Table 5 for each band of the MAIA multispectral camera.

Band	K_0	K_1	K_2
Band 2 - 490 nm	0.0438	0.0984	0.0041
Band 3 – 560 nm	0.0868	0.1839	-0.0030
Band 4 – 665 nm	0.0624	0.0799	0.0154
Band 5 – 705 nm	0.1207	0.1874	0.0016
Band 6 – 740 nm	0.2552	0.4829	-0.0672
Band 7 – 783 nm	0.2957	0.5407	-0.0986
Band 8 – 842 nm	0.3064	0.5142	-0.0906
Band 9 – 865 nm	0.3634	0.5333	-0.0862

Table 5. K_0 , K_1 and K_2 of the Ross-Li model for each band of MAIA multispectral camera when observing vegetated surface.

The BRDF computed by the model are shown in Figure 30 and they are compared with the BRDF measured (Figure 26).

Figure 30. Left column: polar plots of the modelled BRDF. Right column: polar plot of the measured BRDF collected by MAIA multispectral camera the 30 April 2021 over vegetated area.

From Figure 30 we can assess that the Ross-Li model, inverted with the data collected by MAIA multispectral camera over vegetation, reproduces quite properly the reflectance anisotropy of vegetated surface. However, the BRDF polar plots modelled (left column) appear smoother than the ones based on the collected measurements (right column), and thus seems that the model can't exactly simulate the BRDF in each point even if it takes the overall trend. Nevertheless, as mentioned above, it has to be underline that measured BRDF could be affected by errors due to the slight change in the illumination direction during the flight (see also 7.3).

The comparison between modelled and measured reflectance is also shown in Figure 32 (see 11.1 in Appendix).

7.4.2 BRDF Model – Asphalt Surface

In this section, we present the BRDF model generated from the MAIA multispectral camera data when observing the asphalt surface (mission of the 3 July 2021, see Table 4).

After the processing of the BRDF values for the collected measurements, the first step which must be done in order to invert the model, is to compute the kernels of the model (F_1 , F_2) for the specific acquisition geometry. This has been achieved by means of a Python code already existing.

Knowing reflectance (R , MAIA measurements) and kernels (F_1 , F_2) for different Sun-viewing angles (θ_s , θ_v , φ), the parameters of the model (K_0 , K_1 , K_2) are estimated and listed in Table 6 for each band of the MAIA multispectral camera.

Band	K_0	K_1	K_2
Band 1 - 443 nm	0.1687	0.1232	0.0168
Band 2 – 490 nm	0.1709	0.1303	0.0195
Band 3 – 560 nm	0.1959	0.1342	0.0232
Band 4 – 665 nm	0.2143	0.1329	0.0257
Band 5 – 705 nm	0.1953	0.1168	0.0240
Band 6 – 740 nm	0.2001	0.1221	0.0239
Band 7 – 783 nm	0.2124	0.1182	0.0247
Band 8 – 842 nm	0.2151	0.1139	0.0263
Band 9 – 865 nm	0.2417	0.1260	0.0291

Table 6. K_0 , K_1 and K_2 of the Ross-Li model for each band of MAIA multispectral camera when observing paved surface.

The BRDF computed by the model are shown in Figure 31 and they are compared with the BRDF measured (Figure 29).

BRDF Modeled Polar Diagram - Band3_560nm

BRDF Polar Diagram - Band3_560nm

BRDF Modeled Polar Diagram - Band4_665nm

BRDF Polar Diagram - Band4_665nm

BRDF Modeled Polar Diagram - Band7_783nm

BRDF Polar Diagram - Band7_783nm

BRDF Modeled Polar Diagram - Band8_842nm

BRDF Polar Diagram - Band8_842nm

Figure 31. Left column: polar plots of the modelled BRDF. Right column: polar plot of the measured BRDF collected by MAIA multispectral camera the 3 July 2021 over asphalt area.

Looking at Figure 31, we can assess some conclusions as the previous case. The Ross-Li model, inverted with the data collected by MAIA multispectral camera over asphalt, captures the overall trend of the measured BRDF. However, the model probably simplifies the reflectance anisotropy of the surface; it simulates indeed the expected peak of reflectance in correspondence to the Sun position and the lower reflectance values in the opposite side of the polar coordinate system respect to the Sun position, but it seems that it can't precisely reproduce the punctual values of BRDF. Nevertheless, as already mentioned (7.3), the measured BRDF values in correspondence to the cross points, can be affected by errors due to the shift of the Sun during the flight.

The comparison between modelled and measured reflectance is also shown in Figure 33 (see 11.2 in Appendix).

8 LESSON LEARNED

The experience collected during the execution of IDEAS-QA4EO project (WP2175) highlights the following remarks, which are considered baseline to address the challenge of IDEAS-QA4EO activities:

- Cooperation between different scientist from different domain of expertise (geophysical experts, data scientist, UAV designers and operators, lper/Multispectral instruments developers) is a prerequisite to succeed. We recommend ESA to keep supporting the creation of such ecosystem and project opportunity where interaction among different domains are promoted and required.
- UAV market is experiencing a rapid development, then the exploitation of UAV potential requires knowledge on the state of art solutions, in order to speed-up and optimize the operations.
- Access to in-situ data is a key for research development. Actually, UAV have potentials to collect dataset using sensors with similar characteristics of satellite multispectral sensors, with the advantages of strong flexibility in terms of geometry of acquisition, spatialization of the information, spatial resolution and selection of the test sites. Moreover, UAV acquisition campaigns has cheap costs. We encourage ESA to further extend their resources towards the creation of UAV dataset with specific peculiarities, in order to create integrated solutions to improve and optimize the quality of satellite data.
- The UAV system has an intrinsic level of uncertainty coming from on board sensors in charge of positioning (GPS, barometer, compass) and sensor noise. This has to be clearly evaluated, in order to optimize modelling of BRDF.

8.1 Way forward

The WP2175 has received positive feedbacks and interest from the scientific community that have expressed interest in hosting our UAV system to SRIX4VEG initiative (<https://frm4veg.org/srix4veg/>). In this context, we'll contribute towards global community-agreed guidelines for UAV-based surface reflectance product validation.

The main interests arise in exploiting the UAV for multispectral acquisition with Sentinel-2 likes sensor, in order to investigate:

- BRDF modelling;
- Further developments of MAIA multispectral camera capabilities;
- Cal/val activities on Sentinel-2 data;
- Create a training dataset based on UAV acquisition for AI SuperResolution algorithms dedicated to Sentinel-2 data.

A possible approach for a project follow-up is already under evaluation and will include the improvement of system capabilities, the selection of new test-sites with different land cover and the comparison of BRDF model parameters with the ones derived from MODIS sensor.

9 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

9.1 Highlights

The WP2175 produced a UAV system equipped with multispectral camera Sentinel-2 likes able to perform automatic surveys acquiring data with different view azimuth and zenith angles. The system has been designed to execute and repeat planned missions. The survey has been accomplished over two different test sites presenting vegetated and paved surface respectively. The datasets have been used to derive polar plots of the reflectance value for each band, also evaluating the variation of the spectral signature varying the geometry of acquisition. Considering RossThick-LiSparse (Ross-Li) semiempirical linear BRDF model, we use UAV dataset to derive the kernel parameters and produce synthetic polar plots. The results show an excellent agreement with theoretical literature and similar activities with on-ground instruments.

9.2 Technical Developments

A new system of acquisition have been made-up, in particular:

- MAIA camera and ILS module have been installed on UAV platform;
- The UAV flight unit have been connected to the sensor and programmed to interact with it;
- A specific support have been adapted to allow the remote control of the view zenith angle of the camera.
- Specific flight plans have been designed and developed to optimize and automate the acquisition survey.

9.3 WP management

The project has followed a scrum agile methodology based on monthly sprint and weekly stand up; Monthly, Quarter reports have been delivered to ESA.

The activities have been delayed due to COVID-19.

9.4 WP deliverable

ID	Title	Milestone
D-1	UAV Dataset	Sept 2021
D-2	Validation report and scientific roadmap	Oct 2021
D-3	Contribution to QA4EO MR and QR	
D-4	Presentation to QA4EO Cal/Val WS	

9.5 Outreach

The WP has submitted a conference paper titled "UAV-BASED OBSERVATIONS FOR SURFACE BRDF CHARACTERIZATION" to IGARSS 2021 and arranged a demonstration day in airfield "FlyRoma" for ESA cal/val team.

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11 APPENDIX

11.1 Comparison model/measurements – MAIA data on vegetation

Band 2 – 490 nm

$R^2 = 0.88$

Band 3 – 560 nm

$R^2 = 0.81$

Band 4 – 665 nm

$R^2 = 0.83$

Band 5 – 705 nm

$R^2 = 0.76$

Band 6 – 740 nm

$R^2 = 0.65$

Band 7 – 783 nm

$R^2 = 0.61$

Band 8 – 842 nm

$R^2 = 0.58$

Band 9 – 865 nm

$R^2 = 0.55$

Figure 32. Comparison between modelled and measured reflectance over vegetated surface for each band of MAIA multispectral camera.

11.2 Comparison model/measurements – MAIA data on asphalt

Band 1 – 443 nm

$R^2 = 0.83$

Band 2 – 490 nm

$R^2 = 0.78$

Band 3 – 560 nm

$R^2 = 0.84$

Band 4 – 665 nm

$R^2 = 0.85$

Band 5 – 705 nm

$R^2 = 0.85$

Band 6 – 740 nm

$R^2 = 0.84$

Band 7 – 783 nm

$R^2 = 0.86$

Band 8 – 842 nm

$R^2 = 0.87$

Band 9 – 865 nm

$R^2 = 0.85$

Figure 33. Comparison between modelled and measured reflectance over asphalt surface for each band of MAIA multispectral camera.